

Neuro - Leadership: Exchange of Ideas with Dr Neuropsychonomist

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Respected Dr Neuropsychonomist.

Trust, this dialogue finds you in the best state of health and spirits, wherever you are Our Mentor.

We are writing to you after reading a book titled 'Thinking Fast and Thinking Slow' and a book titled 'Noise' by a good friend, Dr Daniel.

We wish to initiate a dialogue with your learned scholarship in the following few pages, please.

Please bless us.

**Jyoti and Kalpana
India**

Well, Dr Neuropsychonomist, behaviourism is the mirror that reflects penchants, philosophies, and other psychological states. Choice making is a rudimentary human action. Choices craft anthropological (and business) lives. The arena of (global) business is time and again acquiring a multifaceted, multifarious, complicated and a knotty architecture with wide - ranging and vigorous, originality and novelty that has developed as a catalyst for performance and concert for business and business management albeit the problematic settings. In such a mosaic of conditions, it becomes vivacious to fruitage powerful, astute businesses that generate enthusiastic doppelgänger of business leadership.

The world of management is in acceptance to the fact that the classical boundaries, frontiers borderlines and front lines between undercurrents of economics, psychology, commerce, markets and business has amalgamated into a unified scholarship notably; Neuromanagement. Neuro - management challenges customary management postus. This 'New World' has embraced covertly

and overtly embraced the world of neuroscience, neurobiology and multidisciplinary science (undercurrents of heredity, genetics, molecular biology and cellular sciences) that syndicates neurophysiology; all five sense organs included. This cumulative dynamics (science of 'choice behaviour' concept of 'thought') has embraced allied physiological mechanics like gut feeling, emotions, eye tracking, eye tracing, eye gazing, heartbeat, blood chemistry skin conductance and along with the dynamics of choice making has given birth to an 'Era of Neuromanagement'; that symbolises a spate of bio (economic) - revolution. This has in fact generated waves that obligated choice behaviour and accretion of choices. Not to forget is the association of considerations of Darwin's Survival of the Fittest (best 'fitted,' or best 'adapted,' to its atmosphere is most likely to occur).

Humans take choices by conforming to laws of rationality incorporating the paradoxes. For any economist, analysing choice centers on the world of prediction. Based on strong axiomatic pedestals, arguments profess 'should' or 'could' directives primarily based on a strict regimen of algorithms. These generated normative theories. Psychologists appreciate psychological constructs that escort choice making. They predict behaviour and capture 'mental events' that go beforehand choice. Neuromanagement appreciates neural architecture alleyways and designs to reach at choice making compartment. Irrespective of the scholarship angle, aim is to select as a course of action and arrive to a solution that ends uncertainty (or imperfect knowledge) or dispute in course of choice making. This act is primarily centered on 'expected utility' dynamics. It is perceived that

some amount of (cognitive) bias does seep in the process. This is for the reason that some element of bias, gut feeling, tastes, preferences and belief / faith coupled up with intuition (reference is Drawn to concept of 'Quasirationality'; juxtaposing diagnostic thought and perception) does make way into choice processes. It is here that brain; sense organs, heart, skin, blood and eye have a role to play in gathering real time information and aiding real - time choice making. Issue is, is there an extraordinary function for neuromanagement or neuroeconomics, and, if so, what are its suitable exploratory philosophies?

Is choice making 'rectilinear' with straight lines and shapes? Is choice making 'curvilinear' depicting some different connotations? Are choices representative(s) offshoots of molecular movements offering flexible and accurate alternatives along 'choice pathways'? Is choice making 'Autotrophic' crafting its own procedural protocols? Is choice making 'heterotrophic' crafting procedural protocols from external 'Agents'? Is choice making 'Saprotrophic' depending on protocols from external 'Agents'? Is choice making an assembly of well - defined 'Symmetry of Torics' with moment angled manifolds and complexes? Do all these reflect some degrees of combinatorics? Business leader has to take choices with insufficient experimented facts. It is stimulating to compare several courses of action and select one to be executed. The question is does the brain oscillation between actions? Why do business leader choice researchers undertake experiments? Is it to test a notion or outcome implications with experimental observations? Does abstract representations aid comparison or plots in the sensorimotor map have a round about? Is it to establish empirical regularities as basis for new notion(s)? Is it for comparing choice settings? Dynamics of Eye movements and Blood monikers are 'catalysts' of neuro business leader choice. When business leaders sort choices, they commit deviations in their signature behaviour. In neural computational simulations, each business leader choice task is signified by protuberance of neural activity. Choice red neural activity has constituents of spiraling of activity and choice initiation to overcome choice to be completed. It seems like there is a scattered accord transversely planes of portrayal. One way is to scan business leader choice behaviour. Blood Monikers and Eye Movements are crucial measure indistinctly concomitant to choice reflection. Both are chromatic prospects for rational processing

which measures and calibrates to reveal or reflect what business leaders are contemplating.

This Dialogueoutmaneuvers basic safekeeping that neuroscience, neuroeconomics and neuromanagement cannot sway business modeling. This norm or code is on 'Behavioural Sufficiency' (causative circuit elucidations of behavioral external stimuli dimensional challenge) and 'Emergent Phenomenon' (soupçon corresponding to connections that harvest qualitatively innovative topographies not initiated in its integral fragments physiognomies of necessity and independence) guiles. Each experience perceived by brain, blood and eye(s) are in sync with transferences of neuronal activity achieved by each event being perceived as evidence from neuro - mechanisms. This provides conceptual geometry for conducting neuro - business leader translational research science. It rears few fundamental issues and offers solution through measurement of brain, blood activity at management levels of analysis (Satpathy and Gankar; 2016).

Business leaderprototypes are fundamentally instantaneous with operational originality. Voyaging through 'bustamination' ('business' and 'contamination'), business leader is diagonally at cater - cornered with neuroscience, neuroeconomics and neuromanagement. Business leader thereby covertly and overtly communicates a perceptive organised linkage ('Chess Board Matrix') perceived as 'nonconforming approximation' with business replicas' and 'disruptors'. This is chaotic 'noise' that calls for 'Business leader Choices'. There is domineering need to embrace variegated and propagation perpetually embracing neural mechanisms of perceptual practices fundamental to state of 'Homo - Neuropsychoeconomicus. This buttons 'Homo Economicus' by replicating how technology receptive business leaders are influenced by psychological, molecular, genomic and (neuro) cognitive conformations (involved in representation and selection of choice opportunities).

Of interest is how business leader brain captivates to acclimate to inform and improve business leaderchoice mechanism in a state of complexity and uncertainty (or imperfect knowledge). With crossbreed choice making prototypes, questions are; Do business leaders actually, grounded on facts, figures, data, information and statistics have a choice? How do they skim off on an action in a state of unbounded 'scrolling' and perpetual 'disorders'? What 'neuro

pointers' and 'neuro - monikers' re to amenable conclusions? Will neuro business leader dynamics usurp orthodox cognitive arrangements associating neuro - integrated courseto reconnaissance neuro - milieus in 'business leader' choices? As a trade-off between accurateness and explicate ability, experiments based on methods and approaches from Eye Trackingand Blood Monikers physio-diagnostic data have been offered that encompasses porches of biological basis of preferences traveling significant role of 'neuronic' in crafting business leader neuro - based preference flight path. This translational research communication attempts at ad Dressing how neuro apparatuses explore business leader preference making.

Enthusiasm

Well DrNeuropsychonomist, is designing prototypes of cognition an efficient means of answering business leader choice? Methodology is based upon deductive inter - disciplinary review approach. As a dynamic between theoretical and applied business leader choice dynamism, attempt has been to combine conception and experiments. This is to undertake task of disentangling subtleties and implications of distinction between risk, 'deep' uncertainty and ambiguity. To make a choice when strata - layering is ambiguous, all possible layering of situation have been factored. Information across categories is integrated. Attempts employ multi - method approach and triangulation. Drawn on positivist and interpretive conceptual paradigms. This likens methodology to building with 'foundation' (philosophical premises), 'pillars' (consisting of conceptual research approach / strategies / 'inferential' data collection / dialogue matrix) and 'subsidiary inclusive structure' (operational architecture). This starts from theoretic inter - disciplinary review leading to specificities. It is a waterfall - based ('Top - Down') approach.

Motivations for this Dialoguewas on account of the fact that human brain is a bioelectric organ that has gradually allowed social and neural sciences to effect a marriage and share a common concentration. Choice making is critical for any business leader when crafting and executing strategies.

Well DrNeuropsychonomist, Interconnection plays central role. What typifies notion of causation in sciences of mind and brain? Are dissimilar notions a prerequisite for different experimental approaches? Are there variances in notions that are explicitly and implicitly presumed? What counts as causal evidence in business leader choice sciences? What role is played by

information and physical mechanisms in identifying causal claims of business leader sciences of mind and brain? Documentation of molecular and genetic markers precisely forecast rational physiognomies for appreciation cognitive and neural mechanisms of individual choice making. An emerging new paradigm, through brain's wiring diagram, Dialogue adopts to examine potential cause - consequence linkage between biology (neurobiology of choice making) and management in explaining how business leaders deal in choice dynamics.

Well DrNeuropsychonomist, human beings seldom make decisions on a random note. Central motivation is to go up in price nature of a hybrid scholarship that serves as central or business leader assumptions rather than theories. Considering the above, based on neural underpinnings, raise the following questions: Is a theoretical charter missing in business leader neuroscience? Moreover, if not, to what magnitude does it have a theory? In what ways does theory or conceptual architectural framework it has compare to those of more established sciences? What consequences might these differences have for a reasoning of neuroscience? The bottom contour is: Can there be reasoning of neuroscience without a broad or successful theory? All these prompted to explore the links between business leaderchoice making and neuroscience. Perceptions into mechanisms help develop an important question; what is then the role and connection of neuromanagement? What do brain, blood and eye(s) tell about management? How is the big picture for neuromanagement going forward? choice making involves forming a perceptual representation of choice base.

Well DrNeuropsychonomist, there are four major enthusiasms for this dialogue of translational research: -

- First, few management investigators are passionate to study character of neuromanagement in business leader choice making dynamics. Herein exists an opportunity to undertake an examination into the subject.
- Second, neuromanagement translational research arrange for new way of computing business leader choice. This provides stimulus to undertake an dialogue.
- Third, neuromanagement serve as 'catalyst' for model development.
- Fourth, 'inferential' information and neuroscientific representations stimu to start a fresh dialogue into the subject.

- Fifth, neuromanagement provides ways to test choice observables and computational (neural) mechanisms?

Neuro - Gamut

Some decisions by human brains are influenced by atoms of irrationality, molecules of impulsiveness and particles of emotions. Neuro - Continuum has encompassed business atmosphere and human organisations with neuroscience and business spreading a linking that seemed an uncharacteristic guesstimate. There is a 'heterodoxian noise' for a disruptive strategy to make choice making a reality via unconventional strategy. Hybrid intuition - based (reference is Drawn to the concept of 'Quasirationality'; juxtaposing diagnostic thought and perception) 'disruptive mental' approximations' models are emerging as alternative to model complex systems under improbability. Do business leaders have all data they need? Are business leaders still using precise models? Is there new analysis or heterodoxian insight that could make business leaders operative? Crucially, do business leaders choose what stroke to take? What heterodoxian physiognomies of substitutions aid intuition - based 'disruptive mental' approximations'? How to help business leaders cultivate choice and intuition - based 'disruptive mental' approximations' skills? Will heterodoxian neuromanagement replace conventional management? This Dialogue intends to explore an elucidation linked to 'busitagion' scenario via cause and effect linkage.

DrNeuropsychonomist, behavioural management has shown that business leaders do not always work in ways that management theories envisage. Business leaders, as humans, are subject to of thoughts, attention, logic, mirror image and speculation. Brain has been a subject of the evolutionary processes. All these subscribe to a series of emotions? In such milieu, how are brain, blood and eye(s) systems responsible for choice making process? Is it correct and precise to think of brain, blood and eye(s) as calculating device? Does scholarship profess and acknowledge as to what should neuroscience or neuromanagement inherit from computationalism (neural mechanisms)? How to craft laboratory and field based, as deemed appropriate, experiments to study choice making in choice - demanding situations? In specific, how does biology, neuroscience and neuromanagement provision and oblige choice making. These questions include tenets from psychology, behavioural management, cognitive, neuroscience and allied subjects. This is the new signature

paradigm in business leader choice dynamics with logic advanced from dissimilar approaches using divergent methodologies. What neuromanagement prepares, one would be prudent enough to just endure to coat it as a black box? All above trends towards inference that neuromanagement is a perfect podium to exhibit that neuro -business leader sciences, can provide answer to issues in business leader choice dynamics. It is significant to arrive at a deduction that neuroscience, and neuromanagement, follow 'Biological Plausibility' (contributory linking flanked by acknowledged derivation and conclusion that is unwavering with ubiquitous biotic appreciation). DrNeuropsychonomist, The dawn of substantial progresses has fashioned capability to scrutinize anthropological brain at an insightful glassy, yet scholastic and applied significance of prevailing confirmation centered on neuroscience procedures and approaches contained by pitch of business leadership rests unmapped. Some issues from the discussions are as under;

- How to version confirmation about value, probability, risk, ambiguity and timing?
- How do above parametric indices perform?
- What distinguishes when criteria adopted are disparate?
- Are there any straight connexions that exist between the above tactics?
- How perceptible variables impact assortment of choice making criteria?
- Is there any link between peripheral variables and choice norm used?
- What kinds of set of rules and calculations underpin choice process?
- Which zones of brain, blood and eye(s) are implemented at neural level?
- How is management business choice made in intricate environs?
- How management sciences harness neuro - digital 'inferential' data for rational dialogue?
- What are the crucial 'neuro - ordered' domains and allied protocols?
- What mutual links occur between cognitive and effective processes?
- What are the neuro - behavioural management underpinnings?
- How does valence of evidence have emotional impact on choice?
- How do responsive and affective agents' / design parameters influence?
- How changes can be expounded by neuro - behavioural management?

As regards **discrete differences**, some business leader predicaments are;

- How do unconnected changes influence choice-making?
- How do stimulus and goal - orientation impact?
- What neuro - systems provision dissimilar motivational states?
- What neuro - behavioural processes differentiate 'adaptive and affective adaptive and affective agents' of choice?

As regards **circumstantial stimuluses**, some business leader quandaries are;

- How do circumstantial connections encourage, provision or dent choice?
- How business leader standing influence choice?
- What are the effects of norms, pressures and stigma?
- What adaptive and affective adaptive and affective agents influence process and quality of choice?
- How precisely are paradigms supposed to be encoded in neuro - physiological structures?
- How can discernments from neuromanagement be implanted?
- What has neuromanagement sponsored on 'adaptive and affective adaptive and affective agents' not being rational?

Investigational concerns that aid in exploring the above issues are: -

- How does business leader decide in a state of Vacillation, Risk and Probability?
- How does business leader decide in state of Uncertainty, Vulnerability, Complexity and Ambiguity?
- What neuro - biological monikers aid in deciding?

Principal Objective

DrNeuropsychonomist, the principal attempt launched in this research Dialogue was to cast eye on tumultuous, issues engulfing world of business and primarily that of choice processing. Care has been allotted for 'disruptive mental' approximations'. This is from a principle - based outlook to report research problem based on empirical study. Principal aim is to model business leaders' choice making by using tools from neuro - management. This translational Dialogue presents neuro-business leader science of management modeling approach. This is to create evidences for multiple systems involved in business leaders'

choice-making. Besides principal objective, following objectives are taken into consideration for present translational research work;

- Criteria (physiognomies that each alternative own) adopted for choice making,
- Methodology of assessing cases for choice making,
- Variables that emphasizes choice making,
- Choice perspectives as regards (UVCA), and
- Conduct neuro - based interpretation on business leaders' choice making.

DrNeuropsychonomist, the backbone of this Dialogue that embodies translational research depicting link between management and business leaderneuromanagement is to explicate how choice makers inter-disciplinary field translational research makes choice by integrating management science, economics, neuroscience and psychology. Attempt encompasses irregularities that are gainsay with traditional business leader hypotheses, appraise choice making by combining methods such as behavioural, neurophysiological, experimental economics and develop choice models based on neural and psychological mechanism. Scope underlines previous and present translational research progress regarding each perception and res it to scope of this Dialogue. This Dialogue ad Dresses perceptions, theories and models from cognitive science, psychology and biology standpoint. The scope ranges from business leaders of small, medium and large units

Hypotheses

DrNeuropsychonomist, the hypotheses, adopted and tested are;

- Choices are made based on measurable and idi osyncratic results,
- Neuro undercurrents are obligatory to dynamics of business leaders' choice,
- Business leaders' harbour gradation of analytic thinking than pragmatic thinking style,
- Business leaders are susceptible to cognitive biases during choices and,
- Business leaders' face intuitive perceptive during choices.

Methodology Dr Neuropsychonomist

Neuroscience is the new order in 21st Century neuro-business leader decision dynamics. Meandering along among finite or infinite alternatives, research was conducted with use of theoretical and experimental approaches according to a procedure consisting of selecting a

research question, searching relevant and pertinent literature from management science databases, choice making process and experiments of neurophysiological techniques like blood moniker analysis and eye tracking (adopted as a Test Case - cum - Pilot Study) as effective tool for experimental research. Based on an inter - connected and hybrid pathway, methodology adopted has been to develop theoretical foundations, models and systems to provision choice making in highly complex, dynamic systems, operating in uncertain, resource-constrained situation. Although, based on neuro - operations translational research procedures, this translational research attempt includes multi - disciplinary emphasis to accommodate complex, multi-dimensional choice architectural frameworks. DrNeuropsychonomist, for this purpose, methodology adopted is outlined below.

Conceptual translational research has been directed with use of literature inter - disciplinary review method consisting of following stages: -

- Choosing theoretical translational research queries,
- Literature probe in neuro - controlled 'inferential' catalogues,
- Congregation of selecting relevant literature, and
- Summarising

Empirical journeys DrNeuropsychonomist, well, methodology comprises of inter - disciplinary tests on:

- Character of 'Blood Signatures' and 'Eye Movements' in business leader choice mechanism,
- Empirical treatment of 'Blood Signatures' and 'Eye Movements' in business leader choice mechanism, and
- Introduce association between business leader choice 'adaptive and affective adaptive and affective agents' / design parameters'.

On focal radar were issues like, how to read minds (brain mapping), how to read facial expressions (anthropometrics), choice making ability (eye tracking and blood) and adopt style of management in future. Moot question is what insights can behavioural science give us about business leaders and reactions / interplay with those business leader's lead? A sample of 150 representative business leaders) in Bhubaneswar have been chosen. Basic assumption is that samples

so selected out of population are best representative of population under study.

DrNeuropsychonomist, this research incorporates stratified sampling methodology. The research architecture has been stratified into gender and age groups. Each echelon has been experimented as a self-governing sub-population, of which specific rudiments have been designated casually. This has facilitated to arrive at conclusions and interpretations about unambiguous subcategories that would have been lost in case of indiscriminate illustration. Such exercise facilitated a package of statistical estimates. By means of stratified sampling, approach was deemed to be appropriate than accumulating data transversely towards groups. Since each stratum was viewed and subsequently treated as self-determining populace, dissimilar sampling tactics has been adopted to dissimilar strata, theoretically empowering use of methodology best suitable for each acknowledged subcategory within populace.

Data DrNeuropsychonomist, Data,

Primary data and knowledge has been collected through process of pre-tested questionnaire, personal interviews and focus group interviews, personal observation, projective techniques, pilot survey to improve questionnaire, structured questionnaire, statistical choice sampling and naturalistic observation. Some part of the data was obtained from experiments conducted in Taiwan and a few papers were published of these. For empirical part, data has been collected through blood chemical analysis and eye training apparatuses. Blood analyzer equipment has been for blood parametric analysis and for eye movement analysis, Tobii equipment has been used. **Secondary Data and Knowledge** has been chosen from web sources, business journals, dairy and desk sources etc. Engine Searches, where wide knowledge about different areas was easily available, was relied upon. Data were also corroborated from archival records and diary translational research sources

Tools and Techniques

DrNeuropsychonomist, **Questionnaire:** It was proposed to implement open-ended questionnaire. Paper - and - Pencil Questionnaire administration, Computerized Questionnaire administration and Adaptive Computerized Questionnaire administration were contempd for purpose of gathering information from respondents. Due to pandemic situation, questionnaires were

floated through personal mails and some were floated through personal contacts.

DrNeuropsychonomist, **Statistical Techniques:** Once data / facts / information were obtained from primary and secondary sources, these were clinically tested through Blood Analyzer and Eye Movement Monitoring methodologies to establish a co - relation between variables aimed at typically summing up discrepancy between observed values and values expected under the model in question. The results have been corroborated about business leaderschoice making: dependency on characteristics, choice making biases and deliberate / intuitive reasoning approaches. Data obtained has been treated through;

- **Test:** Determine differences between means red in definite structures,
- **ANOVA:** Analyze differences among group mean and difference of variability,
- **Blood Analysis :** Check on physical and chemical properties of blood sample, and
- **Eye Movement:**Investigate dynamics of eye movements.

DrNeuropsychonomist, The Dialogue

Is designing prototypes of cognition an efficient means of answering business leader choice? Methodology is based upon deductive inter - disciplinary review approach. As a dynamic between theoretical and applied business leader choice dynamism, attempt has been to combine conception and experiments. This is to undertake task of disentangling subtleties and implications of distinction between risk, 'deep' uncertainty and ambiguity. To make a choice when strata - layering is ambiguous, all possible layering of situation have been factored. Information across categories is integrated. Attempts employ multi - method approach and triangulation. Drawn on positivist and interpretive conceptual paradigms. This likens methodology to building with 'foundation' (philosophical premises), 'pillars' (consisting of conceptual research approach / strategies / 'inferential' data collection / dialogue matrix) and 'subsidiary inclusive structure' (operational architecture). This starts from theoretic inter - disciplinary review leading to specificities. It is a waterfall - based ('Top - Down') approach.

The first question, Dr Neuropsychonomist, in questionnaire, pertaining to psychological linkage, concerns with 'Openness to Experience'. Question was aimed at soliciting views as regards vigorous imaginings, ocular understanding, focus

on inner feelings, penchant for variability and rational inquisitiveness. Question was posed from point of view of human personality as depicted in conventional 'Five - Factor' Model. Aim was to observe whether business leaders were receptive and welcoming new ideas, fresh approaches and innovative thought processes. It was conjectured that any business leader who was 'high' on 'Openness to Experience' would be a go - getter / risk - taker on path of business - adventurism.

DrNeuropsychonomist, responses in Table - 2 is suggestive of the fact that majority of business leader - business leaders in Group 1, 2 and 3 accord more than 72% as regards multi - faceted, resourceful, deep, reflective and knowledgeable factors are concerned. Range is between 72% to 91%. But, as regards factors like 'rational' is concerned, range is between 61% to 64%. As regards 'unproductive' factor, range is between 09% to 12% and 'unchallenging' factor commands a range between 27% to 34%. Group 1 being an appreciably young age, they seem to establish powerful cognitive reflections (absorb in supplementary consideration). Same trend is somewhat parallel in case with Group 2. There is some degree of lop - sidedness with Group 3. Comparable argument stands valid for Group 3, 4 and 6, respectively. It is circumstantial that high percentage of business leaders belong to 'creative - flock' (massed together). These elements are carriers of unambiguous cognitive aptitude, intellectual, ocular and emotion - laden engagement. There is a Drive to engage in philosophies, cogent - oriented and sense of openness (genii by which brain gets evidence). These open opportunities for creativity. This abundance of input is equally matched with ounces of output. In such a scenario, element of decentralized choice making atmosphere is projected.

DrNeuropsychonomist, above exploration can be focused on brain dynamics in that openness to experience is allied with distinction in brain assembly. They are comprehensive in thinking, spread - out in how they process information and those with higher percentage on any of above factors tend to reason and act resourcefully. They view world of business creatively different. Their brains and mind harbour significant ocular and cognitive responses. There is an experiential superior 'extensiveness, penetration and penetrability of business and choice awareness' and inclination to 'cognitively reconnoiter' intellectual information (ideas and arguments) plus sensory 'inferential' data. All these lend a significant part in

shaping business choice making inventiveness. The role of 'chromosomal - influence' is factored at this stage of exploration.

The second question, DrNeuropsychonomist, pertaining to psychological linkage, concerns with 'choice to join business'. When issues are being debated as regards changing work - life balance, VUCA, changing dynamics of work, market fluctuations, anxiety etc., why is it that prompted business leaders to join world of business? This question was engaged to solicit the business leader mind set to join vocation of business. A set of 29 'appealing - factors' were offered to entire cluster of business leaders whose response percentages are shown in the Table - 3. Question was aimed at soliciting views with simple options of 'Agree' or 'Disagree'.

Advances in neuromanagement offers packages of modules like 'Neurofeedback' and 'Capito' models as to how training for the brain and brain for training act and interact amongst themselves. Broadly, DrNeuropsychonomist, these have an umbilical connect with Neuroleadership as defined by business leader personae. Indicative of comprehensive skills for business leader development, aimed at holistic skill set and mind - set, was the first option offered to business leader - business leaders. It is experiential that 94% of male business leaders and 91% of female business leaders have opined in favour. Inference drawn is that training is a catalyst towards cultivating subjective efficiency and team concert. This is envisioned critical in direction of client connections and inclusive business progress. Issue is how is brain concerned about training perspectives in business arena? Corollary is that a positive mental attitude in business is indispensable. It is learnt from neurosciences that patterns of brain activity changes subsequent to training. Attention is drawn to 'Capito Model' by Thomas Feiner of Institute for EEG Neurofeedback (IFEN), Munich (Germany) which is recommended for future researchers but outside the scope of this Paper. Slight shift in dynamics of brain activity does reflect adoption of control strategy. It is conjectured that business leader - business leaders are quite alert to comebacks as regards emotions of stake - holders. They allot space towards turning possibilities and probabilities into near - perfect outcomes and results. Business leaders, Dr Neuropsychonomist, are (perhaps) attentive towards mind - set, relationships, perception, influence and thinking. They are tactical Agents, trendsetters and transformation Agents. They are

dedicated to distinction, pellucidity and exactness. Training seizes opportunity to capture emotional reactions that help initiate unconscious judgements. Demand for training is up - curve as business leaders who are at top edge of curve see that emotion does influence business performance. Neuro - scientifically, training leads to swing in sensory motor information from slow to fast and alleyways. Training results in separation of neuronal ensembles generating self -regulating torrents of information handling. Effectual multitasking develops through prefrontal cortex.

Economic life, Dr Neuropsychonomist, as characteristically considered by self-centeredness, convenience and profit escalation. 'Long run profit maximisation', in gamut of variable costs of factors of production (land, labour, capital and organisation) was second option offered to business leader - business leaders. It is experiential that 78% of male business leaders and 59% female business leaders opined in favour. Inference drawn is that business leaders aim at profit maximisation in short as well as in long - run, DrNeuropsychonomist. This can be an exception as regards philanthropic organisations. Given techniques of production, choice of techniques, favourable and non - advantageous factors, business environment, regud price, input, and production planes, it is an undeniable fact that principal aim of commercial entity is to spiral profit intensification. If business leaders are registering usual profits in short run there will be development of productivity and they presume to see new competitors in market. These act as pointers for re-arrangement of capitals.

DrNeuropsychonomist, neuropsychology embraces that there exists strong link between profit maximisation and survival in unpredictable business. When profit maximisation is reliable with high rates of persistence, business leaders adjust conclusively towards optimal state. When survival and profit maximisation are counter balancing, business leaders improve effort to persistence rates. Comprehensions into tenacious sequences of affluence and out of order are reflective as to how brain aims at equilibria thereby influencing choices. A significant conjecture is that non - conformities from profit maximization cannot help business leader to survive long in playground of business. Observation is that 59% of female business leaders have opined in favour. On lines of argument presented above, it is experiential that 94% of male business leaders and 79% of female business leaders favour maximisation of sales. Similarly, 91% of male business leaders and 66% of female business leaders have opted for

improving market shares as intent to join business. Likewise, 87% of male business leaders and 53% of female business leaders opted for maximisation of shareholder value. Neuroscience holds that emotions are influencing factor in business dynamics. A thought process is that these business leaders are happy, satisfied and contented with roles in business play and life, in general. 'Symptomatic Bias' is experiential here. These are experiential methodical designs of non - conformity from standard or judiciousness in choice making. This is adequate to thwart process of choice and need is to identify, challenge and inject innovative dosages. These forecasts of strong relevance for 'ordering' business leader elements of future.

Business leaders, DrNeuropsychonomist, continuously attempt to act in phase - wise manner of eternal business surveillance and intuitively poised based on business information. Strategic intelligence enables to control things that thwart prospects. Business leaders are supposed and expected to be 'good' business citizens. Corporate Social Responsibility was third option offered to respondent - business leaders. It is experiential that 12% of male business leaders and 18% of female business leaders have opined in favour. Likewise, for option of service to Society, 16% of male business leaders and 37% of female business leaders have opined in favour as reason to join business. It is experiential that as regards corporate social responsibility and service to society are concerned, opinion is somehow a state of near - balance. With such falling percentages, choice to join business appears to be strong by majority of business leaders.

Branded as 'Business - Conscience', DrNeuropsychonomist, corporate social responsibility (whether right or wrong) is supposed to take care of socio - economic and environmental concerns of stake - holders. It is significant towards ushering in (internal) business environmental invigoration, Dr Neuropsychonomist. This is aimed at business - profit and social welfare balance. These promote sense and satisfaction of business accountability. There appears to be a mind - set that social responsibility reduces profit margin as such projects do not lend towards rising profit curve. Business leaders pronounce that such schemes mean 'stealing of rightful assets'. They need to focus on bottom line towards survivability. In view of profit maximisation psychology, there exists no repudiating potency of this dispute. Irrefutably, corporate social responsibility has been accorded low priority. This section can be

branded as objectivity, evidence, quantification; rationality as far as corporate social responsibility is concerned. Dr Neuropsychonomist, rational approach 'left brain' is recognized to be 'weak'. Concentration is on business profit maximisation rather than social responsibility agenda. Hence, low proportion of business leaders opining social responsibility reason to join business stands evidenced.

As regards reason to join business, Dr Neuropsychonomist, opportunities to develop through challenging and interesting work found favour with 79% of male business leaders and 55% of female business leaders. It is boost for any firm to offer challenging and interesting work to business leaders. This is aimed at human resources management and development that ultimately leads to organisation development. In a fast - paced, dynamic, erratic nature of economy and challenging business world, these act as top 'Motivating Agents'. In case obverse is experiential, then it is a wake - up call for management of work dynamics and environment. An impressive high percentage of business leaders opting for these options are suggestive of the fact that 'mind set' to perform are high on joining business organisation. It is indicative DrNeuropsychonomist, that business leaders are ready to move out of their 'comfort zones' and jump across periphery. Management of potential, with respect to 'Optimal Anxiety' is call of hour.

As regards option of 'reasonable chance of promotion if I work hard', in current scenario, is concerned, found favour with 32% of male business leaders and 45% of female business leaders. This seems to be a discouraging response. An interesting 'inferential' data set is experiential. There seems to be an air of pessimism. Is it that business leaders felt that they lack cutting edge skills and expertise to compete with modern forces of business competition? Is it that business leaders lacked some bundle of professionalism? Is it that business leaders have failed to erect adequate backing in net of advisers, backers, and envois around them? Is it that business leaders DrNeuropsychonomist, failed to distinguish zones that could be used to register improvement? Is it that business leaders have anticipated a 'Grey Ceiling'? Was it a mere temptation to opt for such an option whose final results read '32% for male business leaders and 45% for female business leaders'. This can be discounted DrNeuropsychonomist, as an aberration. Nonetheless, micro - neuroscience based treatment may reveal that business leaders, in this paper, can

ward off with this pessimistic tone if they develop air of aficionado. This is presented from point of view of role of emotion in choice making. Business leaders are performing keeping in view that 'brain is never truly at rest'. Robust optimism is alley forward towards progress. Perhaps, based on analytic and scientific thinking, concept of 'Transcendence' (based on a 'Gut Feeling'), not definable in terms of customary appreciative or experience, still keeps them performing as effective and efficient business leaders. Inference is that business leaders perhaps have put their faith on intuition (reference is drawn to the concept of 'Quasirationality'; juxtaposing diagnostic thought and perception), certain that choice to join business is a viable intention?

Universe is a harbour of unlimited choices that generates fountain of ridiculously high expectations. 'Expectation to grow with career path clearly mapped' found favour with 44% of male business leaders and 57% of female business leaders. Presently, DrNeuropsychonomist, many educated people are coming with idea of joining early start - ups where expectation to grow with career is clearly mapped out or at least a blue print is available. There is a set of well - defined purpose, Dr Neuropsychonomist, vision, goal, skill, knowledge, attitude, competence, networking, mentorship etc. where career path is well - projected. This is a clear cut case of career mapping. Dr Neuropsychonomist, an ideal career path is diagrammed along dotted lines. These lead to prescription in progression of jobs, traditional straight up career striking order, dual occupation striking order and level occupation frameworks. Business leaders feel that such resources are premeditated to help recognise skills and aptitudes to advancement within business domain. Issue DrNeuropsychonomist, is; how is brain a catalyst in depicting expectation to grow in career path? Fact is that such expectation takes birth from environmental and societal realisms. When one participates in cognitive information flow, it is by default that blue print appears to decide as to what is required to subsist in business world. In fact, 'attention to thriving' gains ascendancy. Since 'expectation to grow with career path' is a course of action, brain starts journey in unmapped terrains. It is factored DrNeuropsychonomist, that figures of 44%, in respect of male business leaders and 57% in respect of male business leaders, respectively is may be due to experiential and unexperiential forces of VUCA. To lend credibility, an interesting observation is that as far as 'opportunities to develop through challenging and interesting work'

option is concerned, 79% of male business leaders and 45% of female business leaders have opted for the same.

Dr Neuropsychonomist, Peter Drucker has voiced, 'Wherever you see a successful business, someone once made a courageous choice.' Wilfred A. Peterson voiced, 'choice is the spark that ignites action. Until choice is made, nothing happens. Choice is but courageous facing of issues, knowing that if they are not faced, problems will remain forever unanswered.' Option was offered pertaining to 'I come to work purely to get business done'. Interestingly, 96% of male business leaders and 87% of female business leaders have opined in favour. This clearly sparks element of 'dedication' and 'commitment' as far as business leader - business leaders are concerned. This seems to be a visible, transmittable passion, attitude and character, initiative and work ethics DrNeuropsychonomist. There is perhaps an idea to bring about a metamorphosis from urge to practical reality. Neuro - based judgements report that letting passion die is the worst episode than not possessing passion at all. Business leaders are perhaps subscribing the quote, "There is far more opportunity than there is ability" (Thomas Edison) and 'Don't worry about failure'. You only have to be right once" (Drew Houston). Captivatingly, 85% of male business leaders and 84% of female business leaders have preferred to opt for option 'My loyalty is defined and I feel a part of a team in businesses. This subscribes to neuroscience of trust in joining business. There is a sense of loyalty, brains hardwired to trust, air of evolutionary psychology (explains mental and psychological traits) besides allied reasons that have prompted them to join business. Such forces design adaptation to changing conditions and patterns of choice behaviour. This apparently, Dr Neuropsychonomist, provides cognitive suppleness to acquire from practices, monitor business world based on calculations and fine - tune activities when estimates are viod. From neuro - science angle, this is a case of neuro - plasticity (either way; functional as well as structural) that depicts changes in brain of respondent business leader to adapt behaviour in face of changing demands. Path is critical to developing choice stratagems. Strong parallels are experiential between understanding of business leader brain and how businesses work. These must have prompted business leaders to join business.

Brain is, DrNeuropsychonomist, basis and carter of emotions and behaviors. Grit is a successful venture only if immersed in controlled -

perseverance and controlled - passion. To lend credence, it is experiential that as regards, 'I feel reciprocated efforts put in by me', 77% of male business leaders and 59% of female business leaders have designated in favour. It seems that big motivation for business leaders was 'norm of reciprocity'. There is subscription to the fact that 'inferential' data on brain function and structure employ unique supremacy and stimulus in emotional status that aids in choice making. This appears to be a state of honoured web of commitment. Dr Neuropsychonomist, as regards motivation to contribute cent percent to business for future benefits, 96% of male business leaders and 89% of female business leaders have designated in favour. It is neuroscientifically established that motivation guides behaviour. It involves and capitalises upon biological, responsive, societal and reasoning forces. Even opportunity of 'chance to learn new things in my work' has been supported by 89% of male business leaders and 92% of female business leaders, respectively. Chance of achieving something worthwhile has been supported by 93% of male business leaders and 91% of female business leaders, respectively. Option of 'chance to use my abilities' has been supported by 94% of male business leaders and 87% of female business leaders, respectively. Option of 'Supplementary options like 'I will work for business indefinitely registered favour with 78% of male business leaders and 79% of female business leaders, respectively. Dr Neuropsychonomist, option of 'carrot and stick policy' has received unexcited response with 57% of male business leaders and 68% of female business leaders, respectively. Business leaders were perhaps aware that there exist explorations and observations which certify that human behaviour is influenced by change efforts and threats and infrequently prosper in long run. Option of 'being able to change things' ('Change Management') has been chosen, Dr Neuropsychonomist, by 91% of male business leaders and 88% of female business leaders, respectively. Also, 'I work to achieve goals of businesses was preferred by 98% of male business leaders and 94% of female business leaders, respectively. This may have elicited spirits of acknowledgment. Perhaps business leaders are aware that above line of reasoning makes it conceivable to shape ongoing interactions and interfaces. Hence, strong choice to join business.

Mankind is 'under a cowl of mindful attentiveness', Dr Neuropsychonomist. A couple of soft - option like DrNeuropsychonomist; 'business

leaders in business evaluate different management practices' has been preferred by 69% of male business leaders and 71% of female business leaders, respectively. Additionally, option of 'business in high concert organisation' has been opted by 94% of male business leaders and 92% of female business leaders, respectively. These options were offered from point of view of business leader psychology and ascertain as to why business leaders were inclined to join business. It is gestimated that business leaders are aware of intrinsic and extrinsic aspects aligned to soft - options offered. 'Having a say in matters of businesses' has been preferred by 95% of male business leaders. 91% of female business leaders have opined for the same. It is presumed, Dr Neuropsychonomist, that business leaders are under influence of being administrated by subconscious routes as well as unconscious route paths. Supporting the proposition is option 'choice to remain involved' which has been chosen by 93% of male business leaders' and 91% of female business leaders. Consequently, a strong choice to join business.

Human beings have got boundless potential and are hardwired for regeneration and reinvention by injection of fresh perspectives, new experimental models, new technologies and innovative pathways of operations. Final option 'business harnesses your potential' has been preferred by 79% of male business leaders and 76% of female business leaders, respectively. Is this master - option a strong choice to join business DrNeuropsychonomist,? It can be safely inferred that business leaders are aware about neuroscience of leadership. They are apparently aware of practical strategies they would encounter as an business leader. They are enthusiastic towards better understanding to advance business leadership behaviours. They are self-aware, proficient in motivating and appealing towards business goals.

As regards 'proficiency about choice making' is concerned, options offered were, no proficiency little proficiency, average proficiency, 'good' proficiency very 'good' proficiency and rich proficiency. The readings indicate increasing order of 'overall' choice proficiency as experiential Table 4. It can be inferred prima facie that choice making capacity of business leaders seems to grow with each passing age. 'inferential' data was cold by amalgamating responses received under heads; no proficiency little proficiency, average proficiency, 'good' proficiency very 'good' proficiency and rich proficiency. This may primarily be linked to

business experience, business acumen and business awareness. In age - group of 25 - 40 years, figure of 51% for males and 49% for females is experiential. This is self - explanatory as business leaders are in their initial stages of business leader responsibility and there can be some room for inconsistency of actions which can impinge choice process. It is conjectured that there could be unpredictability in performing practices, displacement of responsibility and the like. In age - group of 41 - 55 years, we observe a figure of 68% for males and 54% for females. As can be experiential, in age - group of 56 - 70 years, we observe a 87% for males and 73% for females. It can be safely assumed that choice maturity by these business leaders could be, overtime, acquired by spotting choice behaviour of fellow business leaders. In phonology of neuroscience, prefrontal cortex is the last that develops fully. This 'definitely impacts 'executive choice'. Neuroscience enables explore dynamics of brain to understand how women and men decide differently. There are authentic differences in brain structure, responsible for ability to function, between them. Neuroscience establishes that prefrontal cortex modifies its edifice and role in response to experiences. This is reflective of supplementary unfolding of genetic choice making blueprint. Such flexibility and protracted growth provides prospect for incessant adjustment of cognitive 'choice' function (through combination of brain organisation, hormones plus 'neurotransmitters'). These direct choice making command in 'hard - disk' of brain.

Pertaining to 'Person - Business Fit' options offered were; 'Personal values are 'good' fit with business', 'Business has same values as I do with regard to concern for others', 'Business has same values as I do with regard to honesty and ethics' and 'Business has same values as I do with regard to fairness and justice'. These are presented in Table - 5. There is overwhelming response from all categories of age - groups as regards option of 'Person - Business Fit'. In age - group of 25 - 40 years, we observe 71% of males and 69% of females have voiced in favour of 'Strongly Agree'. In age - group of 41 - 55 years, we observe 88% for males and 84% for females have voiced in favour of 'Strongly Agree'. In age - group of 56 - 70 years, we observe figure of 97% for males and 93% for females have voiced in favour of 'Strongly Agree'. There is perhaps general arrangement that business leaders make choice by using expectations, philosophies, behaviours, mentality and approaches. Value congruence leads to optimistic consequences. Factual worth of 'value

congruence' is when it is put into framework. Research is yet to provide valid instrument to extent 'Person - Organisation Fit' or 'Value Congruence'. Possible instrument of judging is through deep semi - structured interviews that possibly may divulge how business leader views values and assesses these. Interestingly, some neuro - based studies establish a relationship between 'Business leader - Organisation Fit' and 'Career Success' plus 'Satisfaction'. With age, maturity and development, notion of 'Person - Business Fit' is on ascendancy. These may prompt business leaders towards 'good' 'choice making' ability. Hypopaper in neuro business leader research; 'Brain Makes the Fit' is quite pertinent here. This is because, Dr Neuropsychonomist, businessleader neuroscience accepts the dictum that behaviours are driven from cataleptic somatic processes in brain. This paper recommends further research in 'business leader - organisation fit implementation', 'success factors' and measures. This ricochets Nagel (1974) who said, 'it may be impossible for us to abandon certain ways of conceiving and representing ourselves, no matter how little support they get from scientific research'.

As regards 'Work - Personal Interface' Dr Neuropsychonomist, option was 'business philosophy defines how to operate business', 'amount of work responsibility and norms of performance are centered on business', ties with present business are difficult to break and are central to existence', 'business shows concern and cares about opinions and well - being' 'business strongly considers goals and values' and 'help is available when I have a problem. There is a metaphysical touch, Dr Neuropsychonomist, to this questionnaire item with 'that resonates'. Observations are presented in Table - 6.

It is experiential that more than 70% of all age - groups in each gender have opined to strongly agree for options offered. Conventionally considered as province of social philosophy, these options reveal flashes of neuro-theology and neuro-psychoexploration. It seems probable that in VUCA, there appear some elements of 'consciously cultivated trust'. Trust is pedestal on which entire edifice of work - personal interface revolves. This is an ideal strategy, Dr Neuropsychonomist, for inter and intra - organisational choice oriented work flow. It gives idea that 'business psychology' or 'occupational psychology' is influencing business leaders. There appears to be a flow of balance between somatic, psychological and emotive dynamisms. This

certifies 'single mindedness on development mind set'. This has apparently led to stable attention, better attention and mediator judgements ('creative ability'). Studies find neurobiological substrates in using neuroscience towards optimising philosophy of trust interpositions on brain to endure reasonable improvement in choice behaviour. This paper calls for experiments in future measuring trust, changing environment of trust and trust as critical success factor in organisations. These do aid in choice process.

As regards 'Profit and Wages', Dr Neuropsychonomist, options offered were; 'reward procedures in business are fair, 'if I work hard and am productive, I am compensated by profits, 'I have plenty of opportunities for growth / reward, 'those who deserve rewards receive them with fairness', 'business will notice if productivity or work quality declines' and 'are you satisfied with amount of profit you generate'? This questionnaire item is oriented to motivation to join / continue in business leader profession. Observations are presented in Table – 7. It is experiential that as regards options offered, male business leaders in age bracket 25 - 40 years are secured at 74% closely followed by their female counterparts at 59%. With maturing age and experience, Dr Neuropsychonomist, figure steadily rises to 78% and 74% in case of male business leaders. On the other side, figure rises to 87% and 73% in respect of female business leaders. It is obvious that with dynamics of market economics, business leaders must have shifted their options for continual business leadership skewed in favour of profits ('profit motive'). By introducing fresh ideas and by infusing business with injections of innovative practices, business leaders perhaps feel that think that profit maximisation is a prime motivation in business leader behaviour. It has been opined that as regards, 'reward procedures in business are fair, 'if I work hard and am productive, I am compensated by profits, 'I have plenty of opportunities for growth / reward, 'those who deserve rewards receive them with fairness', 'business will notice if productivity or work quality declines' and 'are you satisfied with amount of profit you generate', profit motive is locomotive that certifies progress of business leader discipline.

Dr Neuropsychonomist, as regards option, 'How satisfied were you with overall business benefit package', observations are presented in Table - 8. True passion germinates from package of strong belief. This might end up in embracing satisfaction. This is a direct reference to 'ultimate concern' or 'grit'. When aspirations, objective and

targets are met, brain feels satisfied (brain releases dopamine which propels one to feel satisfied). On an average of different age groups, by incorporating facets like 'very satisfied', 'satisfied', 'neutral', 'dissatisfied' and 'very dissatisfied', it is experiential that in age group 25 - 40 years, 76% of male business leaders and 71% of female business leaders have opined in favour, respectively. In age group 41 - 55 years, 81% of male business leaders and 79% of female business leaders have opined in favour, respectively. In age group 56 - 70 years, 88% of male business leaders and 83% of female business leaders have opined in favour, respectively. Such trends reflect 'biologic reinforcements 'through evolutionary approaches to business leader choice behaviour. This appears to be indicative trend pertaining to client satisfaction. Neuroscientific studies indicate that orbitofrontal activity and brain parts like, prefrontal cortex, orbitofrontal cortex, ventral pallidum, cingulate cortex, insula, nucleus accumbens, substantia nigra and ventral tegmental area are linked to satisfaction. This aid in choice making for business leader. This paper is of the firm notion that synpaper of evolutionary and psychological 'Agents' promise generation of plausible models of business leader choice making.

Dr Neuropsychonomist, rationality prescribes that business leaders should gather evidences as regards alternatives. They should examine pros and cons. Also, they ought to cautiously consider factors, and as a final point, come to a functional judgement. Options like, were offered to factor in biases and shortcuts pertaining to complicated procedure of choice making. Multifarious neural paths are formed besides being redesigned during evolvement of brain. Do business leaders weigh 'plusses' and 'minuses' before deciding? Options offered were 'recurrently', 'intermittently', 'occasionally', 'hardly ever' and 'certainly not'. It is experiential that such act promotes deeper thinking. Observations are presented in Table - 9. Above statistics show that an appreciable 75% and above of all business leaders have chosen for options like 'recurrently', 'intermittently'. business leader brain analyses as to what lies between 'inferential' data and result expected or anticipated. An associated item in questionnaire was 'do you decide on your own'? The observations are presented in Table - 10.

It is experiential, Dr Neuropsychonomist, that figures between options, 'business leaders weigh 'plusses' and 'minuses' before deciding' and 'do you decide on your own'

is near - tallying. Statistics show that appreciable 75% and above of all business leaders have chosen for options like 'recurrently', 'intermittently'. There appears to be a correlation between both the concepts. It is a stated truism that choice making is a skill; easy for some, difficult for others and not so easy for many. Choice making is tough and brain wrestles between options and alternatives to guide towards 'choice'. Dr Neuropsychonomist, Brain helps business leaders compute 'expected value'. Brain utilises dorsolateral prefrontal cortex, orbitofrontal cortex anterior, cingulate cortex (ACC) and ventromedial prefrontal cortex for such mechanisms within a specific span of time. It would be safe to assume that limbic system plays a major role in choice making process.

Dr Neuropsychonomist, on issue of 'Do you take 'intelligence' over choices selected', business leaders are presented in Table 11. 'Inferential' data offers interesting results. 88% of male business leaders and 77% of female business leaders in age group 25 - 40 years feel that intelligence can be passed over choices selected. Percentage appreciably rises for both genders as age cohort rises. This merits some discussion. It has been scientifically proved, Dr Neuropsychonomist, that genetics plays imperative role than environment. Correspondingly, brain function and arrangement re to intelligence (inter - oriented with each other). A clinical exploration as regards 'phases' of choice making divulges 'intelligence' as a search 'Agent' for setting a call in choice dynamics. Business leaders who are intelligent are assumed to be endowed with ability to think and reason. So why this variation in statistics above? Perhaps, answer lies in the fact there exists 'discrepancy of intellect within species or amongst diverse species'. This is based on underpinnings of 'neural basis of intelligence' and 'brain case or brain volume' ('cranial capacity'). This has relationship with choice making. This paper asserts association between inherent brain events and brain volume.

A significant option was to gather 'inferential' data as regards 'psychological time' element in choice making. Two inter - oriented questions were asked; one, 'Do you deliberate when psychological time is at premium' and 'Do you plan in adequate psychological time - frame'? This exploration plotted observations and observes that 'psychological time' element has been plotted above 90% by both genders of all age groups in cumulative fashion. Neuroscientific posits subscribes that span of eagerness possibilities replicate choice making in business leader brain. This

incorporates, Dr Neuropsychonomist, incentive programming, perceptual cataloguing, response assortment and reaction presentation. 'Psychological time' dimension includes appraising substitutions that vary on a set of characteristics, traits and characters. Such a 'Play' centers on extent of possibilities, length of anticipated deferment for appreciating options and 'psychological time' obtainable to grasp a business leader choice.

Other items in questionnaire inquired about 'Do you factor in 'ancillary' choice choices', when deciding, do you provision for 'first - look option', is your choice administered by principles? Answers were 'Recurrently' by almost 79% and above by both respondent groups. Cumulative responses are experiential over 73% for both genders. Ancillary choice choices supplement main process of business leader choice making. 'Inferential' data, Dr Neuropsychonomist, obtained from ancillary brain Blood flow analyses, ancillary eyes analyses, ancillary heart beat analyses and ancillary eye movement analyses do support clinically choice mechanism. These are tested in experimental inferences presented in this Paper. These helps answer supplementary demanding questions in choice designing.

Other items, Dr Neuropsychonomist, in questionnaire solicited responses as regards, 'do you talk about choice making to others' and 'do you often change your mind? The young business leaders, of both genders, in age group 25 - 40 years have responded in affirmative to the tune of 87%. This is obvious as business leaders observe that to frame sustainable choice and ensure mid - course corrections, consulting peers and superiors is 'safe bet'. Business leaders, Dr Neuropsychonomist, perhaps conjecture that consulting helps revitalise business, generate business model and come out on winning side of in choice and 'deep' uncertainty. Rigidity spells deceleration. 'Mental flexibility' aids them conceive strategic plots, feedback, independent thinker, analytical mind set and web of synergy. Also, it helps in evolving strategic goals and augment bidding stratagem. Such results, Dr Neuropsychonomist, corroborate through Electroencephalography (EEG) and Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) tests. As regards, 'do you often change your mind, it can be experiential as open door policy or attitude towards inviting fresh ideas and models. In such a situation, brains are engaged through engagement of amygdala or hypothalamus. These initiate 'flight' or 'fright' response. Research suggests that fresh 'inferential' data help change mind when it pertains articulating to daily choices. This supports new thinking and strong emotional experiences. This paper subscribes to a quote, 'minds are simply what brains do'.

Do you make choices without seeing implications'? This item was striking by low - affirmative responses with each age group marking less than 50% replies. It can be well experiential that business leaders are aware of implications of VUCA and its effects. This menace is a significant 'factor' to be factored in business choice making. On platform of fast changing dynamics and information overload ('Mental Effort'), consequences are pre - designed and forecast. Call is for 'flexibility' and 'adaptability'. Business leaders search for solutions to VUCA matrix. Agile business leaders shall 'definitely be well equipped to be successful'. Solution lies in metamorphosis from straight jacket models to problem solving with concurrent philosophy.

To inquire about stability aspects of mind, item posed was, 'do you identify 'control of things' and 'do you remain calm during 'sudden' choices? Coincidentally, almost all business leaders of both genders of all age groups have opined for proposition in 63% - 65% range. All depends on how value information is represented and manner

of such representation. Apparently, business leaders are attentive to business choice, there is need for 'sense of control'. This would factor in near - certainty, culmination of pending requirements, sense of understanding as to how things take shape and of forecasting. This is parallel view that brain discreetly tips 'scale', where preferences Drive choices in choice making. Major role is played by dorsomedial prefrontal cortex here by identifying preference of others than self. All these are estimated in air of trust, faith and belief. It is experiential that 'sense' would minimise forces of VUCA as 'control' ensures 'calmness' during 'sudden choices'.

Human brain is Animal Kingdoms' largest, widest and deepest workshop. Brain uses logic and emotion. One significant information sought from business leaders was on 'gut feeling' with a significant question; Do you rely on 'Gut Feelings' when making choices? This paper is based on presumption that 'gut feeling' is a prime element in business leader choice mechanism. Neuroscience network of gut feeling supports that intuition is shaped by past understandings and familiarities plus information from nerve cells. When brain attempts to 'recollect' or 'retrieve' past information / 'inferential' data, it lays attention on 'gist or theme'. One cannot promulgate heightened ideology simply by one's knowledge or intellect. There has to be equilibrium between 'sentient' and 'static'. Optimal choice is presumed to be arrived through accurate intuition (reference is Drawn to concept of 'Quasirationality'; juxtaposing diagnostic thought and perception). This is considered neuro - based strategy in choice making. 78% of male business leaders and 84% of female business leaders replied that they based choice mechanism on gut feeling. Issue is whether it is rational to trust (conviction) feelings. This is a complicated issue but neuroscience is clearing fog slowly. Different brain regions act, react and interact with various parts to create role played by ventromedial prefrontal cortex in frontal lobe at bottom of cerebral hemispheres. This paper recommends clinical neuroanatomical insight for prospective research and improved understanding.

Behaviour comprises of individual and organisational factors. Belief about how minds work is interesting area of exploration. With availability of big 'inferential' data, artificial intelligence, automation software, cutting - edge technology and management sophistication, choice is confronted by high degrees of VUCA regarding prospective developments of dominating

compound structures. This requires business leaders to incorporate new ways of thinking due to undercurrents of anxiety and fear. Anxiety is central characteristic of business leader functioning. 'To what range better 'industrial relations' aid towards choices'? This is a significant question that was adopted towards this dialogue. Business leaders ranked preferences according to 'very operative', 'greatly operative', 'somewhat operative', 'little operative' and 'not operative'. This questionnaire item was marked with high - affirmative responses of more than 92% responses in age bracket of 25 - 40 years. Figure recedes to 76% and 72% in succeeding age brackets. Neurological mechanisms inform web of correlation between choice making and gamut of industrial relations. Business leaders are receptive to 'business citizenship' and 'business voice' as regards conception and competitive strategies to be pursued. This marks strong correlation of choice contrivance that embraces business leader psychology. This line of argument supports conjecture that choice making is oriented to and based on business leader functioning. Further research on neuroscientific methodologies, agendas, approaches and apparatuses could provide direct measures to get at fundamentals of this dialogue.

As regards 'choice dynamics', almost all (97% of both genders in all age groups) have accorded top ranking to options like 'remain confident to make choices', 'know steps in choice making', 'have feel of commitment to crafting a right choices', 'influence choices with 'certainty' factor', 'make choices under 'time' density', 'control level of concentration', 'think openly and keep pertinent factors', 'narrow down list of options', 'determine assortment of alternative', 'handle quantitative 'inferential' data to classify preferences, difficulties and explanations', 'obtain information', 'weigh consequences of each option', 'evaluate business choice problem situation', 'choose best alternative', 'secure resources', 'make choice and persevere with engagements' and 'refrain from postponing choice making'. A study by Satpathy and Gankar (2016) is reproduced that lends credence; "New brain imaging technologies have motivated neurobusiness leader studies of internal order of mind. We are only at beginning of an enterprise. Its promise suggests a fundamental change in how we think, observe and model choice in context. Brain absorbs information, recognises and frames problematic situations concerning appropriate responses. choice making in neuromanagement is based on complexly

interlinked imaging technologies with links to bandwidth of human choice. business leader often fail to design 'rational' choices. Processes by which business leaders reach choices embody conflicting tenets. Question is how business leader makes choices. How are choices carried out in brain? Interest is on assumptions, beliefs, habits and tactics that business leader uses to make choices. How do parts of brain govern choice-making, coordinate, face obscurity and engage in strategic simplification while deciding? What happens in brain or is activated? Is study of choice-making geometry via neuromanagement relevant? What are the limits? How does previous experience alter behaviour? There are unsolved problems in business leader) cognition. What are the general implications? business leader cognition plays a role. Sensing is as an significant aspect and there is evidence of how evolutionary patterns are shaped by beliefs and attention allocation. How does business leader decide in state of VUCA ('deep' uncertainty, Vulnerability, Complexity and Ambiguity)? In this, neuromanagement seeks to explain choice-making, ability to process alternatives and choose optimal course of action. It studies how management behaviour shape understanding of brain and guide coherent brain geometry towards choice-making? This attempts to explore above phenomenon to put forward a model for neuro-management choice, in which interaction are ad Dressed through measurements of brain activity. Attempt is to model choice-making linking neuro-management of choice behaviour. This provides conceptual geometry for conducting neuro business leader) research at intersection of neuro business leader) science, raises a few fundamental issues and offer solution through measurements of brain activity at management levels of exploration".

Is VUCA the expiration of Strategy and Leadership? VUCA and choice making in arena of business and business leader affairs does have a link with stress. It is generally stressful when one does not know forecast of events or outcome. It commands signal to brain to kick start beginning of cognitive processing. Dialogue was whether business leaders experienced stress consequences. Observation is that young and middle age group suffered most with over 86% of them reporting 'Yes' while elder age group showed some degree of resilience with average of 63%. Correspondingly, similar number or percentages of business leaders have reported that while deciding, they were. Business leaders have reported factors that create choice oriented stress. Business leaders

have cited management, regular fluctuations and amplified assignment as 'primary' causes. Secondary causes are, high degree of 'deep' uncertainty, lack of 'inferential' data challenging demands. Tertiary causes include, goals, long operational hours and commuting time. It can be argued that business leader brains are adequately wired to safeguard from menace of VUCA. Responsiveness of business leader positivity to negativity ratio is imperative. Elder age bracket has shown higher degree of resilience and elasticity because they are calm, collected and encourages confidence. This may primarily be due to age and experience factor. Amygdala helps to harden arteries and handle increased Blood flow for a fight or flight response. Taking a cue, to invoke brain's higher capacity, business leaders can deploy attention to alter brain, cultivate mind set and generate possibilities for tackling VUCA. Future research is suggested through use of 'Opportunity Readiness Level (ORL)' model that promotes ways and means for business leader and, takes care of 'deep' uncertainty framework.

Based on behavioural methodology, 'STAR' ('Situation, Target, Action and Result Method') of interview was adopted in interview phase by presenting a challenging situation (also scripted for the eye movements tests), intrinsic motivation tasks of the business leader, actions and alternatives adopted by the business leader and outcome of business leader actions or reactions. Responses from interviews have been factored where it was felt quantitative gaps could be filled in or some generalisation could be factored in to lend support to logical arguments. Some inquiries investigated during interviews were;

- How much 'time' do you give in choice making?
- How confident are you in correct choice making?
- What pointers indicate that choice making confidence has increased?
- What habits influence choice making?
- What are the 'risks' associated in choice making?
- Do you sometimes postpone choice making?
- Do values and principles play a role in choice making?
- Do choice making align with your priorities?
- Do you guesstimate consequences of choice making?
- Do you change your mind after creating choice making?

- What complexities are intricate in choice making?
- How do you deal with engagements in choice making?
- What steps you anticipate as regards risks in choice making?

Assumptions: Assumptions engaged for this study are;

- Choice is clear and explicit ('Problem Transparency').
- Business leader identifies relevant alternatives('Known Possibilities').
- All substitutions and extents are known,
- Predilections are perfect, persistent and unchanging,
- There is no time or cost constrictions,
- Final choice maximises gainful payoffs,
- Changes are ranked and assigned weights ('Clear Preferences'),
- Weightiness assigned are unchanging over time ('Constant Preferences'),
- Full information is available ('No Time or Cost Constraints'),
- Penchant unconventional yield highest perceived value ('Maximum Payoff'),
- Explanatory schemes can be advanced at neuroscientific and management levels of analysis, and
- There are judicious mappings among above levels of elucidation.

Limitations: Current lack of attainment and determination indispensable for corroborating models are outlined to weak theoretic representation of choice making in contemporary 'assortment. Contemporary models of choice-making are restricted in their capacity to deliver an all - inclusive appreciative of the arena. Limitations envelop two crucial issues. These are primarily methodological and limit neuro - behavioural management conceptual translational research that business leader science has difficulty accepting in. The issues are (i) low influence in existing neuroscientific studies lead to questions over generalisability of results, and (ii) fundamental inability to localise phenomena in brain, blood and eye (s). This Dialogue gauges the predictions for emerging field of neuromanagement to cast light on customary affirmative and normative queries. It contends that possibility for evocative influences, nevertheless frequently misinterpreted and recurrently exaggerated, is however contemporaneous. Limitations encountered during this study were;

- Anthropological aspects posed some manageable limits,
- Literature had to be scanned to study brain, eyes and blood dynamics in business leaderchoice making.

Application of eye tracking methodologies is currently a fresh attempt, world - wide, in brain, eyes and blood dynamics in business leaderchoice making. This Dialogue appreciates that study - involving use of brain, eyes and blood dynamics in business leader is time - consuming than studies encompassing only behavioural responses. Key limitation is that neuro - behavioural management approaches identify those regions of brain, blood and eye(s) that are stimud when business leaders are in constrained situations. These techniques in some way provide full explanation as to why business leaders react in a certain fashion. A synergy between neuro business leader techniques and brain, eyes and blood experiments provide vision into appreciative business leaderchoice making. Alternatives recommended for advancing studies are EEG, Skin Conductance, etc. for better appreciation the dynamics (outside the scope of this Dialogue).

Contributions to Society / Existing Knowledge

- Business leader neuro - management offers insights into nature of planned rationality.
- Business leader neuro - management provisions data in toting to those accessible from conjectural, experimental and investigational research on human compartment.
- Business leader neuro - management offers brain, eyes and blood dynamics- based solution to choice making.
- Outcome of study is beneficial to various stakeholders directly or indirectly associate with business leader decisionactions.
- Study provides conceptual architectural framework for appreciation intersection of neuro -business leader science and business leader choice.
- Study sheds light on reasons of business leader behaviour (and incongruities) that help build theories capable of amplification and forecasting business choice. This has been the principal bed - rock of the theoretical practicalities in this Dialogue.
- Dynamics of brain, blood and eye(s) activity affords information about underlying mechanisms brain, blood and eye(s) during business choice processes.

- Combining above disciplines gives interdisciplinary insight to define fundamentals of neuro - business leaderchoice making that has eluded translational researchers. This has been a primary pedestal of experimental realities in this Dialogue.
- The research findings are important as foundation for future translational research and society at a large would get benefit from this study.

DrNeuropsychonomist, The following deductions were obtained:-

- Hematological provisions instrumental evidence inbusiness leaderchoice.
- Hematological ‘tracking’ is appreciated in technopreneur choice process.
- Hematological arrangements scrutinize choice - task approaches and cognitive capability
- Strong variations in hematological arrangements compartment represent choice certainty
- Observing hematological variables helps identify transitory situations of ambiguity.
- Hematological arrangements serve as calculation technique beyond customary scrutiny.

Psycho - cognitive progressions are prime catalysts to calcu different alternatives and weightages before inching towards a choice.

- Robust link among choice, choice and emotive courses appears to re to approving heuristics; quick and instinctive,
- VUCA (Volatile, Uncertain, Complex and Ambiguous) reshapes business leader world,
- Business leaders in VUCA world cannot have a cinch,
- Business leaders response and perception are part of choice making behaviours,
- Business leaders use perception and skill to sense what should be done,
- Business leaders use intuition courage of convictions to act conclusively,
- ‘Inferential’ data from each subject were analysed independently and observed that error rates were quite low.
- Observations were correct (85%) of the time.
- There was effect of presence of target item and memory set size on response accuracy.
- Real time ‘inferential’ data on correct references follow same pattern of large main effects for both factors: target presence and substantial interaction.

- Slope was significantly influenced by target presence.
- Behavioural results are in strong agreement with dwell time on references.
- Fixations could be interpreted in different ways depending on context and objective.
- During processing of neuro-ocular scene, individuals moved eyes to relevant features in that scene.
- Some features were primarily detected by peripheral area to infer that, 'business leader choice making is unswervingly inter-oriented to instantaneous accessibility, and effortlessness of analysis of pertinent 'material' evidence'.
- Experiments reveal that neurons display saccade-oriented activity,
- Saccade-oriented activity shows steering discernment and setting dependence.
- Results exhibit substantial connection between 'subjective', 'physiological' and 'fixations' from real-world point of view.
- 'Vacillating' business leaders employ additional evidence when attempting a choice.
- 'Definite' business leaders spot on to a choice based on a particular trait.
- 'Vacillating' business leaders take in all of the 'material'.
- 'Definite' business leaders, perhaps, opine that all options have 'good' and 'bad' characteristics. 'Vacillating' business leaders observe and opine that all 'material's had some quota of 'good' and 'bad' points.
- 'Vacillating' business leaders distributed available time over a greater number of attributes during experimental observation.
- 'Definite' participants 'focused' on fewer attributes in order to make their choice.
- 'Vacillating' business leaders spent more time overall looking at nothing.
- Complexity of 'intended' choice problems increases with options and features of each available option.
- Business leaders have full understanding of 'intended' choice problem and adopt optimising behaviour to create 'intended' choices.

Question of how business leaders make choices and judgments continues to pose important challenges for scientific research. This Dialogue summarizes all Dialogues contained in this Dialogue. Dialogue contains salient aspects as depicted in Dialogues titled Introduction, Literature Survey, Business leader Neuro - Architecture and

Experiments with Discussion. Dialogue pools extrapolations Drawn at various segments of Dialogue with analytical discourses. Dialogue suggests fundamental change in biological ('mental effort') Plausibility 'of how business leaders need to think, observe and model business choice in all its contexts. With package of issues for further research, Dialogue attempts to advocate intersection of neuro-business leader science, management and psychology) towards providing conceptual framework for understanding and conducting business leader choice research for choice making.

Thank You, Dr Neuropsychonomist,

Business of choice making is central to business leaders. A complex choice progression takes many stages. Despite inspiring accomplishments, neuro-behavioural management is at best a couple of decades old and is yet to embody critical role in neuro-behavioural management. Researchers are still rhetoric whether neuroscientific 'inferential' information will expansively provide for business leader choice. Focus is on obligatory frameworks for interdisciplinary alliance. Being a maiden dialogue, Dialogue attempts to underwrite towards existing scholarship in following mode;

- Provides frame for appreciating theoretical business leader choice research,
- Offers elucidation through dynamics of brain, blood and eye(s) during choices,
- Describes standard brain, blood and eye(s) based archetype for choice.
- Any business leaders who was 'high' on 'Openness to Experience' would be a go-getter / risk-taker on path of business-adventurism.
- Business leaders, at an appreciably young age, seems to establish powerful cognitive reflections.
- Business leaders at appreciably middle age too seems to establish powerful cognitive reflections.
- Business leaders at appreciably elder age seems to establish comparatively less cognitive reflections with some degree of lopsidedness.
- It is inferred that young business leaders belong to 'creative-flock' and are carriers of unambiguous cognitive aptitude, intellectual, ocular and emotion-laden engagement. There is a Drive to engage in philosophies, cogent-oriented and a sense of openness. All these open doors and opportunities for creativity. In

such a situation, component of decentralised choice making atmosphere is envisioned.

- The phenomenon is linked to ‘brain dynamics’ where ‘openness’ to experience is allied with distinction in brain assembly. Role of ‘genetic - influence’ is factored in at this stage of analysis.
- Training is observed to be a catalyst towards cultivating subjective efficiency in choice making. Corollary deduced is that positive mental attitude in business is an indispensable proposition for choice making dynamics. With patterns of brain activity changing consequent to training and adoption of a control strategy allows space for possibilities and probabilities in near - perfect thinking for choice arrival. Training captures emotional reactions that help initiate unconscious choices. Training leads to swing in sensory motor information through prefrontal cortex. Good training leads to a fine sense of choice making.
- Business leaderlife, as characterised by factors of production is spiral to profit intensification. Neuropsychology holds that there exists strong link between profit maximisation and survival in unpredictable business. When profit maximisation is reliable with high rates of persistence, respondents adjust conclusively towards an optimal state. When survival and profit maximisation are counter - balancing, respondents improve effort to persistence rates. All these influence choice design.
- Business leaders are intuitively poised based on business information. They continuously attempt to act in a phase - wise manner of eternal economic and business surveillance. Strategic intelligence that enables to control things that thwart business prospects. It is observed that as regards corporate social responsibility and service to society are concerned; opinion is somehow a state of near - balance. With such falling percentages, choice to join business appears to be strong by majority of respondents. Correct information leads towards balanced choice design.
- There appears to be a mind - set that corporate social responsibility reduces profit margin as such projects do not lend towards a rising profit curve. Business leaders opine that such projects would mean a ‘stealing of rightful assets’. They need to focus on bottom line towards survivability. In view of profit maximisation psychology harboured by business leaders, there exists no repudiating potency of this dispute. Irrefutably, corporate social responsibility has been accorded low priority. Concentration is more on business profit maximisation rather than corporate social responsibility agenda.
- Opportunities to develop through challenging and interesting work finds favour with business leaders. It is a booster aimed at human resources management and development that ultimately leads to organisation development. These act as top ‘motivating agents’. ‘Mind set’ to perform are high on joining a business organisation. It is indicative that respondents are ready to move out of their ‘comfort zones’ and jump across the periphery.
- Preference for option of ‘reasonable chance of promotion if I work hard’, in current scenario, seems to be a depressing proposition. There seems to be an air of pessimism. Micro - neuroscience based treatment may offer that respondents can ward off with pessimistic tone if they develop an air of aficionado. This is offered from point of view of role of emotion in choice making. Robust optimism is the alley forward towards progress and choice making. ‘Transcendence’ (based on a ‘gut feeling’) scan be introduced as a ‘potent’ as effective and efficient business leaders. Inference is that business leaders put faith on intuition.
- In a world of unlimited choices, there is a spring of ridiculously high expectations. ‘Expectation to grow with career path clearly mapped’ finds favour where at least a blue print is available. With a set of well - defined purpose, vision, goal, skill, knowledge, attitude, competence, networking, mentorship etc. where career path is well - projected, respondents feel that such resources are premeditated to help recognise skills and aptitudes to advancement within business domain. Such an expectation takes birth from environmental and societal realisms which aid choice making. This is because the blue print appears to decide as to what is required to subsist in a business world.
- Business leader sciences have witnessed spread at dawn of 21st Century. Neuroscience conglomerates disciplines to study business leader choice. Value representations describe choice behaviour that challenges empirical results. Each revision unswervingly goads differing evidence. This is reflection of mix of volatility, ‘deep’ uncertainty, complexity and ambiguity (VUCA). One appropriate issue is, does VUCA result in lower choice making

enactment? Prima facie, reply seems to be ‘not necessarily’. It is experiential that information factoring is appropriate when business leaders are processing high quality ‘inferential’ data that is seemingly accurate, well - timed, comprehensive and contributes towards choice making. Although practical circumstances do not parallel to this ‘ideal’ situation, this places or positions business leader on a ‘mode of

calculated caution’. It is vital to understand intricacy of business leader in exploring how brain and eyes choose appropriate responses. In order to explicate neural basis of choice making, capacity to process alternatives and choose optimal course, research combines methods to figure models for answering choice questions. Brain and eyes structure imaging technologies stimulate bandwidth of choices.

Table: 1
GROUPING OF RESPONDENTS

•	Group 1:	Male subjects	(Aged : 25 - 40 years)	Total: 32	} Total: 80 M
•	Group 2:	Male subjects	(Aged : 41 - 55 years)	Total: 29	
•	Group 3:	Male subjects	(Aged : 56 - 70 years)	Total: 19	
•	Group 4:	Female subjects	(Aged : 25 - 40 years)	Total: 31	
•	Group 5:	Female subjects	(Aged : 41 - 55 years)	Total: 30	
•	Group 6:	Female subjects	(Aged : 56 - 70 years)	Total: 09	
•	(Figures have been rounded off) (N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)				} Total: 70 F

Table: 2
OPENNESS TO EXPERIENCE

Factor	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Group 6
Multifaceted	81 %	80 %	76 %	78 %	81 %	74 %
Resourceful	91 %	90 %	87 %	88 %	92 %	86 %
Deep	79 %	81 %	77 %	76 %	84 %	73 %
Reflective	76 %	86 %	84 %	74 %	85 %	88 %
Knowledgeable	76 %	79 %	72 %	79 %	77 %	77 %
Rational	61 %	68 %	64 %	64 %	65 %	65 %
Unproductive	12 %	10 %	09 %	19 %	08 %	08 %
Unchallenging	34 %	31 %	27 %	29 %	32 %	26 %

(Figures have been rounded off) (N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

Table: 3
CHOICE TO JOIN BUSINESS

Factor	Male Agree	Male Disagree	Female Agree	Female Disagree
Training for business skills	94 %	06 %	91 %	09 %
Long run profit maximisation	78 %	22 %	59 %	41 %
Corporate social responsibility	12 %	78 %	18 %	82 %
Service to Society	16 %	84 %	37 %	63 %
Maximisation of sales	94 %	06 %	79 %	21 %
Improve market shares	91 %	09 %	66 %	34 %
Maximisation of shareholder value	87 %	13 %	53 %	47 %
Opportunities to develop through challenging	79 %	21 %	55 %	45 %
I have reasonable chance of promotion if I work hard.	32 %	68 %	45 %	55 %
I expect to grow and my career path is clearly mapped out.	44 %	56 %	57 %	43 %

I come to work purely to get business	96 %	04 %	87 %	13 %
My loyalty is defined and I feel part of a team in business.	85 %	15 %	84 %	16%
I feel business reciprocates effort put.	77 %	23 %	59 %	41 %
I am motivated to contribute 100% to Business for future benefits.	96 %	04 %	89 %	11 %
I will work for business indefinitely.	78 %	21 %	79 %	21 %
I work to achieve goals of business.	98 %	02 %	94 %	06 %
Being able to change things, I do not like about my business.	91 %	09 %	88 %	12 %
Having a say about the way I do things in my business.	95 %	05 %	91 %	09 %
Chance to learn new things in my work.	89 %	11 %	92 %	08 %
Chance to use my abilities within my business.	94 %	06 %	87 %	13 %
Chance of achieving something	93 %	07 %	91 %	09 %
I work for profit and expect to be paid for overtime.	99 %	01 %	97 %	03 %
Business is a high - concert occupation.	94 %	06 %	92 %	08%
Choice to remain involved (so)	93 %	07 %	91 %	09 %
Business harnesses your potential.	79 %	21 %	76 %	24 %
‘Carrot and stick’ approach of motivating works in business.	57 %	43 %	68 %	32 %
Managers in business evaluate different practices of management.	69 %	31 %	71 %	29 %
Above factors, reflect desired values and virtues in business.	77 %	23 %	79 %	21 %
Above factors contribute towards better environment.	89 %	21 %	88 %	12 %

(Figures have been rounded off) (N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

Table: 4
OVERALL PROFICIENCY ABOUT CHOICE MAKING

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	51 %	49 %
41 - 55 Years	68 %	54 %
56 - 70 Years	87 %	73 %

(Figures have been rounded off) (N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

Table No: 5
OVERALL PERSON - BUSINESS FIT

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	71 %	69 %
41 - 55 Years	88 %	84 %
56 - 70 Years	97 %	93 %

(Figures have been rounded off) (N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

Table No. 6
WORK - PERSONAL INTERFACE

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	71 %	69 %
41 - 55 Years	88 %	84 %
56 - 70 Years	97 %	93 %

(Figures have been rounded off) (N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

Table No. 7
PROFIT AND WAGES

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	74 %	59 %
41 - 55 Years	78 %	74 %
56 - 70 Years	87 %	73 %

(Figures have been rounded off) (N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

Table No. 8
Benefit Satisfaction Index

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	76 %	71 %
41 - 55 Years	81 %	79 %
56 - 70 Years	88 %	83 %

(Figures have been rounded off) (N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

Table No. 9
Satisfaction Index

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	79 %	76 %
41 - 55 Years	88 %	77 %
56 - 70 Years	89 %	87 %

(Figures have been rounded off) (N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

Table No. 10
Deciding on Own

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	78 %	77 %
41 - 55 Years	86 %	75 %
56 - 70 Years	87 %	85 %

(Figures have been rounded off) (N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)

Table No. 11

- **'Intelligence' Over Choices Selected'**
- (N = 150 / Male = 80 / Female = 70)
- (Figures have been rounded off)

Age Group	Male	Female
25 - 40 Years	88 %	77 %
41 - 55 Years	89 %	78 %
56 - 70 Years	90 %	80 %

Building a bridge between business leaderchoice making with neuromanagement and neuroscience, this dialogue leads to the

pronouncement that neuromanagement, neuroeconomics, neuro - choice and neuro business leaderchoice is the 'Order' of 21st Century business

dynamics. The flow from biological perspectives of choice making to business leaderchoice dynamics is gaining momentum.

This dialogue has attempted to explore whether neuroscience contribute to business choice management or has it already influenced management with its characteristic positioning? If this is so, what principles about neural apparatuses could have triggered this 'swing' or a shift of conception? In such a scenario, how do business leaders decide in a state of VUCAwhere vacillation is the pivotal phenomenon? Juxtaposed is the issue of role of prefrontal cortex, somatic markers and eye movements in (business leader) choice making. With an eye to gain an optimal choice, how do business leaders bargain 'hot buttons' in business choices?

As regards neural actualities DrNeuropsychonomist, on a bio - choice plane, this dialogue attempts to penetrate into brain - choice reproductions? How can management sciences harness digital 'inferential' data for logical dialogue? What are the crucial geometric domains? Are there direct correlations that exist between external variables and choice criterion approaches? What kinds of algorithms and computations are involved that underpin choice process? What is the character of innovative information (contextual or individual) in disproving or approving choice theories? Reference is Drawn to brain expanse in a definite choice task that endures 'reference'? Tagged along is the role of emotion regulation and emotional intelligence. What consequences might these differences have for a reasoning of neuroscience? Can these be improved by incorporating number of insights from evolutionary theory and complex systems theory?

Scholarship shall stand enriched DrNeuropsychonomist, if future research attempts could cover the following to lend strength to the research dialogue initiated in this work.

- What are the underlying cognitive mechanisms of business leaderchoices and effectiveness?
- What is role of business leader cognitive influence in business leaderchoice making?
- What are the biological bases to bond optimal data, neural activity and choice making?
- What are the causal cognitive mechanisms of business leaderchoices?
- What is the bearing of context and environment on business leaderchoice making?

- How neuroscientific measures in choice 'Drivers' trigger choice behavioural?
- How to sketch 'geometry of alternatives' that govern business leaderchoice?
- What are the methodological aspects in business leader behavioural during VUCA?
- What are the complexities in business leader behavioural during VUCA?
- What appropriate data abstractions in eye tracking help choice representations?
- How to link blood moniker datasets with neuro business leaderchoice mechanism?
- How to link eye tracking and gaze datasets with neuro business leader choice mechanism?
- How to link sweat conductance datasets with neuro business leader choice mechanism?
- How to link olfactory aspects datasets with neuro business leader choice mechanism?

Thank you DrNeuropsychonomist